

Metadata for new_global_wood_decay.csv

Description of data in column headings for the dataset 'new_global_wood_decay.csv' .

Column	Units	Column Descriptor
country	string	Country in which the site is located
site	string	Unique identification code for each site
latitude	number	Latitude of the site in decimal degrees (WGS84)
longitude	number	Longitude of the site in decimal degrees (WGS84)
habitat_type	string	Description of the site
wood_type	string	Type of wood used
wood_origin	string	Identifier for the origin of wood used
N_pc	%	Initial (pre-deployment) concentration of nitrogen in wood
C_pc	%	Initial (pre-deployment) concentration of carbon in wood
P_pc	%	Initial (pre-deployment) concentration of phosphorus in wood
Mg_pc	%	Initial (pre-deployment) concentration of magnesium in wood
Ca_pc	%	Initial (pre-deployment) concentration of calcium in wood
K_pc	%	Initial (pre-deployment) concentration of potassium in wood
Al_pc	%	Initial (pre-deployment) concentration of aluminium in wood
Mn_pc	%	Initial (pre-deployment) concentration of manganese in wood
plot	string	Unique identification code for the plot in which wood was deployed within each site
tag	string	Unique identification code for each wood block
treatment	factor	Treatment of mesh encasing the block (C = no holes cut in mesh; T = holes cut in mesh on bottom of block facilitating termite access; A = holes cut in mesh on top of block facilitating access by aboveground-colonising insects). Note that blocks in the 'T' treatment could go undiscovered and that blocks in the 'C' treatment could be discovered if the mesh was damaged while deployed
deployment_date	yyyy-mm-dd	Date on which the block was deployed at the site
harvest_date	yyyy-mm-dd	Date on which the block was harvested
date_diff	number	Number of days that the block was deployed
initial_wt	grams	Dry mass of block prior to deployment

final_wt	grams	Dry mass of block after harvest
k_value	number	Decomposition constant, calculated as: - ($\log(\text{dry_wt}/\text{initial_wt})/(\text{date_diff}/365.25)$);
termite_discovery	0, 1	Binary score of block being discovered by termites (0=undiscovered, 1=discovered). Blocks were scored as discovered when they were noted as having termites, mudding (i.e., imported soil), and/or damage (e.g., internal chambering, external surface scoring, or removal)
fungal_damage	0 - 4	Fungal damage score using the scale of Davies et al. (DOI: 10.1046/j.1365-2664.1999.00450.x), classifying degrees of damage associated with fungal activity (0 = sound wood; 1 = perceptible but very limited changes; 2 = clear changes to a moderate extent; 3 = severe changes; 4 = breakage of the stake while up-rooting prior to inspection)
termite_damage	0 - 4	Termite damage score using the scale of Davies et al. (DOI: 10.1046/j.1365-2664.1999.00450.x), classifying degrees of damage associated with termite activity (0 = sound wood; 1 = perceptible but very limited changes; 2 = clear changes to a moderate extent; 3 = severe changes; 4 = breakage of the stake while up-rooting prior to inspection)
termites_present	0, 1	Binary score indicating if termites are known to be present on the site (0 = absent and 1 = present)
soil_present	0, 1	Binary score indicating if imported soil by termites was present on the wood block at harvest (0 = absent and 1 = present)
date_diff_years	number	Time in years between deployment date and harvest date
shadecloth	factor	Indication if shadecloth was used to protect the wood block in the experimental set up (yes or no)
dataset	string	Indicates the origin of the dataset (original = from Zanne et al., 2022, https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.19920416.v1 , and new = new salient data)